

Cilfái: Historical Geography on Kilvey Hill, Swansea

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Description

A collection of essays on the historical geography of Kilvey Hill in Swansea (Cilfái in Welsh).

The Hill is an important part of the industrial history of copper smelting in Swansea. For over two hundred years, the Hill was polluted by the copper smoke from Swansea's famous White Rock Copper Works. This book looks at the impacts of pollution and the environmental recovery of the Hill since the pioneering restoration in the 1970s.

Author

Nigel A Robins is a Geographer and author specialising in the historical geography of South Wales. He was a heritage analyst for UK Government and the Palace of Westminster and now researches ancient woodland, landscape history, environmental history and the application of GIS methods and techniques for local history.

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Introduction, Kilvey, Coal and Kilvey, Copper and Kilvey, Pollution and Destruction, Repair, Nature and Restoration

Categories and Keywords

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BISAC Category 3TECHNOLOGY & ENGINEERING / Environmental / Pollution Control

Keywords

Swansea, White Rock, Kilvey, Cilfái, Historical geography, Industrial Revolution, Wales, Kilvey Hill, Environment, Copper smelting, Pollution, Remediation

